

New Die Attach Materials: Silver and Silver/ Copper sintering pastes

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The Power Point Presentation will be available after the conference.

Abstract

Advanced materials, like sintered silver, are key to robust and efficient power modules at high power densities. Excessive temperature degrades the performance and reliability of power electronics. die-attach materials are enabling high power applications to keep temperature within limits, which consequently can allow for higher power densities and lowered overall process cost. In this work, we present newly designed silver-based sintering pastes for pressure-less and pressure assisted sintering applications which enable a high yield of production. Additionally, we introduce a system of cost-efficient Ag/Cu-hybrid pastes, which contain up to 60% of Cu. Results for copper-based materials are showcased for different sintering pressures and validated through mandrel bend and die-shear test. With these new materials industry has the chance to decrease costs of the used interconnection materials with the same stability and workability of Ag-pastes.

1 Introduction

In recent years, a steadily increasing expectation for high-performance materials for power module assembly has been observed in the automotive industry. Due to miniaturization, and constantly increasing power densities and switching frequencies, the performance of interconnection materials such as Sn-based solder is reaching a limit.^{[1], [2]} Despite its attractive price point, soldering is becoming the bottleneck in terms of heat dissipation, electrical resistance, re-melting, and reliability. Especially in applications for eMobility e.g. inverter, power train and charging infrastructure new interconnection materials become more and more demanding to improve reliability, performance and convenience of use.^[3]

Silver sintering as a rising technology is a predestined step for the electrification of modern means of transportation. As a result, on using silver as the interconnection material, a heat conductivity of up to 300 W/ m*K and an electrical resistance of down to 3 $\mu\Omega\cdot\text{cm}$ can be achieved. These physical properties help to reduce the thermal stress which is

induced within modules during operation and helps to improve the lifetime of such interconnects. On the other hand, using silver-based sintering materials often is considered to be a cost driver which constantly leads engineers to look for low-cost alternatives especially within the very price sensitive automotive sector.

Due to its high thermal and electrical conductivity copper is a promising metal for next-generation sintering materials as they are expected to be lower in costs compared to silver-based products.^[4] Wishful thinking from the industry would be to have a material with the exact same workability, reliability and performance, but without the costs of silver. Despite that, with switching to copper, a destabilization of the overall paste system might occur because of the higher tendency of Cu to form oxides such as CuO. To prevent oxidation and reach an acceptable shelf and pot-life of such pastes, the particles in these systems must be stabilized with complex binder materials, coatings, resins or solvents and have to be stored at reduced temperatures. Additionally, the sintering behavior of copper-based pastes is different, which

leads to the necessity to use more complex sintering equipment and newly designed processes. Pressure-less sintering is not only a challenge with Ag-based pastes, but rather more difficult for Cu-based pastes, as the long process time (>2 h) require in some cases not only an inert atmosphere, using hydrogen is mandatory to get proper results and prevent oxidation of the materials. Thus, only pressure-assisted sintering is a route for industry, with the same limitations as in Ag-sintering processes. These factors are cost drivers, leading to a non-competitive overall process cost for the switch to copper sintering materials.

Taking this as a motivation, we developed a material which combines the effortless handling of Ag-based sintering pastes with cost reducing Cu-particles.

2 Results and Discussion

In this work we want to focus on our ongoing developments for Ag-based sintering materials, as we see this as the best intermediate state of development of pure copper-sintering pastes. A significant silver ratio should give the paste system a better stability, workability and processability, as the core silver paste acts as a protective matrix to prevent oxidation of the copper. Consequently, our approach was as follows: Starting with Nano-Join paste NJ-One as the matrix and adding Cu-particles in different ratios. NJ-One as a paste which already has a very high shelf and pot-life of more than six months with a metal content of 92 %wt. For that reason, the system already has a very good mechanism to stabilize small particles and prevent the formation of agglomerates in such a system. The used Cu-particles had been purchased from ABCR and have a size of roughly 4 μm . We added stepwise 10 %wt of that powder into the paste from 20 % to 60 %. In all cases we received a material which was stable for a long

Figure 2: (left) Ag/ Cu-paste with a copperish color. (right) Paste pad of mixed pasted after stencil printing by hand on Cu-DBC.

time at room temperature and had a workability close to NJ-One (Figure 1). Already at low Cu-concentrations of 20 % - 30 % the paste had a copperish color.

Even with high copper content we obtained a stability of the corresponding pastes up to four months and we still could maintain a metal content in the paste of more than 85 %wt. This will help to improve the current shortcomings of copper-based materials and enable industry to generate an improved yield of production and lowered costs per module, which pure copper sintering pastes cannot offer at that stage.

To qualify the properties of these pastes, we conducted a study in which we sintered different components under pressure assisted sintering conditions. In all cases a *budatec* sintering oven was used. Here we had the chance to keep a very good control of the sintering parameters like atmosphere, pressure and temperature. For a standardized qualification of these trials, we used mandrel-bend test, die-shear test and “*glass-die*”-sintering to check on the voiding.

To obtain a good comparability with already existing silver and copper sintering solutions, we sintered in an N_2 -atmosphere with an aimed sintering pressure of 25 MPa, maximum sintering temperature of 300 $^\circ\text{C}$ with sintering time of 10 min and a cool-down time of 5 min. Pre-drying of the pastes was also conducted in N_2 for 10 min at 110 $^\circ\text{C}$.

Figure 1: (left) Sintered components before and (right) after mandrel-bend test.

In a first evaluation, we opted for 5 x 10 mm^2 Si-die with Ag-plating and glass-dies on a Cu-DBC (Figure 2). As shown in figure 2, the results after sintering were promising, as no voiding below the glass-die was visible and the mandrel-bend test showed the desired result of an intact interconnect after bending.

To further understand and quantify the mechanical strength of the interconnect a die-shear studies

was conducted. The sintering profile and the paste were the same as in the experiment explained above (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Shear-dummies sintered on a Cu-DBC.

After die-shear, in all cases a cohesive failure was observed, resulting in an average shear-strength of 90 MPa (Figure 4).

Figure 4: (left) Interface to DBC after die-shear, (right) shear-dummy.

These values are as good or even better compared to silver sintering materials under the same conditions. Compared with copper sintering materials, this newly developed paste system offers an improved workability with competitive mechanical properties.

To stretch the potential of this system even further, the next was to reduce the sintering pressure below 2 MPa. Additionally, we wanted to elaborate the influence of the copper content. To do so, we prepared pastes with a copper content from 20 %wt up to 60 %wt and printed these on Cu-DBCs. Workability was the same for every iteration. Again, similar $5 \times 10 \text{ mm}^2$ Si-dies had been used to qualify the outcome via mandrel-bend test (Figure 5). The sintering atmosphere was nitrogen, the sintering pressure was 1.4 MPa at 300 °C for 10 min, cool down was done within 5 min. Pre-drying was again at 110 °C for 10 min.

Again, the mechanical strength of the resulting interconnect seems to be very strong for all samples as this test is more effective and destructive and therefore causes more damage to an interconnect than a shear test.

Figure 5: (top) Sintered samples, before mandrel-bend test and, (bottom) after. 1 = 20 %wt of Cu; 2 = 30 %wt of Cu; 3 = 40 %wt of Cu; 4 = 50 %wt of Cu; 5 = 60 %wt of Cu.

With the reduction of the sintering pressure down to 1.4 MPa our newly designed copper-containing sintering paste shows the potential of a very potent intermediate material till Cu-based sintering materials will overcome the above-mentioned shortcomings. Usually, Cu-based pastes either require a high sintering pressure to generate high shear strength with short sintering times or processes must be carried out under hydrogen atmosphere for several hours. With a sintering time below 10 min and pressure below 2 MPa and such good mechanical properties industry will be more likely to use such a material.

3 Conclusion

In this work, we had been able to demonstrate the potential of using Ag-based sintering materials and adding up to 60 %wt of copper particles to the paste. This led to a reasonable reduction of material costs. The resulting materials have the same workability as the base material, which was used and only an reduced lifetime of four months at room temperature, which is still high in comparison to the available sintering pastes, either silver or copper-based. The potential to use the materials only with a nitrogen sintering atmosphere simplifies the process for customers of such materials as using hydrogen is not favorable for large volume production. Also, the potential to use the material not only at high sintering pressures of up to 25 MPa broadens the scope of use case, which is beneficial for automotive applications. We see the

potential to develop a material which will work also for pressure-less sintering applications, as we already had been able to reduce the sintering pressure below 2 MPa at reduced process times. This is something we will focus on in a following publication as we see a high demand on pressure less sintering solutions. Industry is trying to substitute soldering in several applications and especially in price sensitive markets. This is something where hybrid pastes will fill the gap between between more expensive silver sintering offerings and “cheaper” copper sintering materials which still require adapted processing parameters.

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